

Advancement in Design of HHO Generator

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Abstract- The usage of fossil gases(like LPG) and the resulting drastic increase in pollution levels has made us realize the need for additional sustainable gas which does not cause pollution. This research ended in an innovative concept of utilizing Brown gas (also known as HHO gas) as a fuel enhancer for LPG gas cylinders employed in cooking activities. Numerous advancements have been achieved in this domain, with various experiments conducted on LPG gas and alternative fuels, utilizing HHO gas or brown gas as performance enhancers. Every day to day life the consumption of fossil fuel and gases are drastically increasing, so this increment of consumption is harmful for environment as well as society. Many factors were taken into consideration, such as; the cell design, especial Cuboid shape, and the plates overall dimensions. Therefore, the main objectives of this study are to perform and evaluate the modelling of different parameters that affect the performance of the HHO generator with Cuboid shape.

Keywords- HHO, LPG, Pressure Transmitter, Cuboid structure

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, fossil gases are considered to be one of the more common energy sources used for cooking purposes, transportation and heating processes. However, fossil gases are useful for daily life but it is limited on earth. In spite of these facts, fossil gases have not yet reached obsolescence, as the world is still facing difficulties in finding other alternative sources and the large widespread. Fossil gases(like LPG) are non-renewable sources, it is important that these types of sources are saved by us.

Many researchers and scientists have conducted many experiments and researches about hydrogen production and usage as a new energy source. Hydrogen is already used in combustion engines as a basic fuel or as a fuel additive. However, practical aspects complicate the common and free use of hydrogen as a basic fuel now so hydrogen is more often used as a refined additive in traditional fuels. It can enhance efficiency and

save LPG. Hydrogen is originated through the process which is called electrolysis of water and is referred to as Hydroxy (HHO) or Brown's Gas. Electrolysis.

In the 19th Century, Michael Faraday gave the term 'electrolysis'. In the early 19th century, many scientists provided research which helped to know about the electrolysis process. The first water electrolysis machine to use hydrogen for combustion engines was invented in 1918 by Charles Frazer. Furthermore, in the 1970's and 80's. Additionally, during the 1970s and 1980s, Yull Brown employed Brown's Gas as a cutting gas and fuel in various industrial applications.

Oxyhydrogen(HHO Gas) will ignite upon reaching its autoignition temperature. In a stoichiometric mixture of 2:1 hydrogen(H₂) to oxygen(O₂), autoignition transpires at approximately 570 °C (1065 °F) under standard atmospheric pressure. The minimum energy necessary to ignite this mixture with a spark is approximately 20 µjoules. Under

standard temperature and pressure, oxyhydrogen can combust when its hydrogen concentration ranges from approximately 4% to 95% by volume.

A stoichiometric mixture can be achieved through water electrolysis, which employs an electric current to dissociate water molecules:

Oxyhydrogen gas has various applications:

Lighting

An oxyhydrogen flame is used to heat a lime-piece to white hot incandescence. Because of the volatility (explosiveness) of the HHO, the limelight has been replaced by glistening electric lighting.

Oxyhydrogen Blowpipe

It produced a hot flame to melt various refractory materials such as Pt, corundum, fire brick, and porcelain and was a valuable tool in various fields of industry. It is used in the "Verneuil process" to get synthetic corundum.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of HHO Generator

Oxyhydrogen Torch

An oxyhydrogen torch (also known as hydrogen torch) is an oxy-gas torch that burns H₂ (fuel) with oxygen(O₂) (oxidizer). It is generally used for cutting and welding of metals, glasses, and thermoplastics. Due to comparison from arc welding and the acetylene-fueled cutting torch, the

oxyhydrogen(HHO) torch is not used frequently in the present scenario, but it is preferred as a cutting option in some applications.

Properties of HHO Gas1

The properties of 'HHO gas' as a fuel are similar to those of hydrogen(H₂), which have been described by Mazloomi and Gomes in their research. Hydrogen is a 'colourless' and 'odourless' gas, whose 'ionisation energy' is around '13.6 eV'. It has a 'liquid-to-gas expansion ratio' of '1:848' under atmospheric conditions. The 'melting' and 'boiling point' are '-259.14 °C' and '-252.87°C' respectively. The 'flammability range' in 'air' is '4-75%', 'flash point' is '-253°C' and 'adiabatic flame temperature' in 'air' is '2107°C'. The presence of hydrogen(H₂) and oxygen(O₂) in HHO gas results in its 'high octane number' presenting a comparison of the significant properties of hydrogen(H₂) with those of 'conventional hydrocarbon fuels'. Santilli presented 'various aspects' of HHO gas which make it a 'promising alternative fuel'. He also proposed that HHO gas consists of clusters of H and O atoms, their dimers H-O, their molecules H₂, O₂ and water vapour. Santilli further suggested that HHO contains a 'magnecular bond' as well as the conventional molecular bond.

Production of HHO Gas 2

HHO gas is generally made by electrolysis of a dilute solution of a significant electrolyte in water(H₂O). This results in the formation of hydrogen(H₂) and oxygen(O₂) gases at the cathode and anode respectively. Further, they are formed in stoichiometric proportions as shown by the chemical reactions equation. The production of HHO gas by electrolysis was indicated by 'brown' (also called 'Brown gas'), which used it for various industrial operations. The design of two electrolytic HHO cells were introduced.

The first type of cell had bi-plate electrodes immersed in a KOH solution and water. The addition of KOH(Potassium hydroxide) enhances the electrical conductivity of water(H₂O). KOH is preferred over NaHCO₃(Sodium bicarbonate) because of its good stability and compatibility with

its metallic counterpart. However, KOH is caustic and dangerous if not handled carefully.

The second design described multiple-series electrodes, in effect forming a number of cells in series. This required less current compared to the bi-plate electrode design.

Brown also used a flash-back arrester to save the harmful flame in the burner from traveling back to the electrolytic cell. Generally, the use of direct current rather than alternating current owing to the lower electrical impedance in the former design.

Carmichael designed an electrolytic apparatus for use in vehicles, boats and aeroplanes. Hydrogen(H₂) and oxygen(O₂) were generated separately in sole upright cylinders containing electrodes and connected by a cross pipe. A unique solution of sulphuric acid(H₂SO₄) and water(H₂O) was used as the electrolyte. This device had a unique float mechanism to move the extent of immersion of the electrodes depending on the level of concentration and quantity of electrolyte. A circuit breaker and maker were provided to stop and restart operation in case the electrolyte fell below a set level. Hydrogen(H₂) and oxygen(O₂) were kept separately in a bifurcated tank and fed to the engine intake via different lines and a suction-actuated valve so as to blend just before entry to the cylinders.

II. MOTIVATION OF THIS RESEARCH WORK

According to research work, our main aim is to decrease the use of fossil fuel and gases. So, use the Brown gas(HHO gas) with LPG to reduce the emission of LPG gas. From the estimation of World Liquefied Petroleum Gas Association (WLPGA), the world uses 317 million tons of LPG. If LPG and Brown gas has 4:1 then the world can save 64 million tons per year(also say that save LPG of 1 year in every 5 years. This data gives motivation to put race forward to use renewable sources.

Various Component of HHO Cell

- HHO Cell(Dry & Wet)
- Bubbler Tube
- Catalyst
- Combined Design(Cuboid Structure)

HHO Cell

There are two different types of HHO cells, dry and wet cells.

Wet HHO Cell

In the case of wet cells, the electrodes in the gas generator became immersed in the electrolyte liquid contained in a container of water.

Advantages-effective gas production, Good stability, easy maintenance, and easy manufacturing.

Disadvantages- needs more current, more heat generated through the cells, and corrosion through the anodes.The heat generated through the cells & the additional current generates more heat, which converts the water into steam. The heat generated through the cells & the additional current generates more heat, which converts the water into steam. The Wet Cell HHO Generator Type is a device for bifurcate water (H₂O) into hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂) when an electric current is passed through the water with good quality of electrodes immersed in an electrolyte.

Figure 2: Wet HHO Cell

Dry HHO Cell

Dry HHO cells are designed to overcome disadvantages of the wet cell type. The result of HHO gas is the same as the Wet cell, but the difference is electrolyte reservoir and electrode plate displacement.

The used dry cell for hydrogen generators has been sealed between each set of electrodes plates to prevent any water leakage from one compartment to another. The bottom edges of the plates are sealed to keep the water from touching them. Dry cell designs are cheaper since they are usually smaller. This design can vary in shape or size and is very easy to install.

Figure 3: Dry Cell

Advantages-Needs less current for each cell due to the volumetric size of the electrolyte within the closed chamber. It is compact in design and for less frequent maintenance. Less corrosion occurs.

This type of HHO cell has many parts:

- Stainless steel electrode
- Soft transparent PVC spacer ring
- Gas vent hole in electrode
- water + Catalyst

Bubbler Tube

The method of bubbler tube uses a source of clean air/gas and is attached through a restriction to a bubbler tube immersed at a fixed certain depth into the vessel. The restriction reduces the airflow to a

very small amount. As the pressure builds, bubbles are released from the end of the bubble tube.

A bubbler tube is a container partially filled with water and HHO gas is fed through one input connected with a non-returning valve and exports the purified HHO gas through port. Bubbler tube is the medium functioning to purify the formed gas, to eliminate all the impurities.

Advantages- Minimal Maintenance.

Disadvantages- Requires compressed air.

Bubbler Tube use following components to purified HHO gas-

- Non Returning Valve(NRV)
- Container
- Nozzle

Figure 4: Bubbler Tube

Catalyst2

There are various catalyst in the industry but for HHO Cell are following-

Potassium Hydroxide (KOH)

KOH is a basic compound, if dissolved in water it will form a KOH solution. KOH will be a catalyst that serves to facilitate the termination of hydrogen and oxygen gas bonds in water. With the addition of KOH solution in water when electrolysed, it is thought that the greater the chance of producing large quantities of hydrogen and oxygen gas.

Similarly, the influence of currents provided by the power source. The larger the current is given the more bubbles that arise from the surface of the electrode. The bubbles are the breaking process of the bond between H₂ and O₂ in water compounds so that H₂ and O₂ increase. Also Eunji Jang, et al (2017) said that KOH is very good at absorbing CO₂. H.H. Masjuki, et al (2016) and Mohamed M. EL-Kassaby, et al (2015) also confirmed that HHO with KOH and NaOH can reduce HC, CO, Nox.

Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH)

Sodium hydroxide is a white dense granular compound and has hygroscopic properties, as well as its reaction with fatty acids to produce soap and glycerol. NaOH is often used in the hard soap making industry. NaOH is one type of alkali (base) strong corrosive and easy to destroy the smooth organic tissue. Sodium hydroxide pure solid white and available in the form of pellets, flakes, granules or 50% saturated solution. It is a moist liquid and spontaneously absorbs carbon dioxide from the free air. It is very soluble in water and will release heat when dissolved.

Sodium Bicarbonate (NaHCO₃)

Sodium bicarbonate is a chemical compound with the formula NaHCO₃. These compounds include salt groups. These compounds are also called baking soda, sodium bicarbonate, and sodium hydrogen carbonate. Sodium bicarbonate is soluble in water. This compound is used in bread or cake because it reacts with other ingredients which will then form carbon dioxide gas, which causes the bread to "expand".

NaHCO₃ is generally produced through the Solvay process, which requires sodium chloride, ammonia, and carbon dioxide reactions in water. The baking soda is commercially produced from soda ash dissolved in water and then reacted with carbon dioxide. Then NaHCO₃ settles. This study attempts to test the effectiveness of the use of the above solutions in producing HHO gas to the exhaust gas emissions.

Combined Design(Cuboid Structure)

Objective

Addition of all the equipment in one cuboid box. Cuboid boxes are used to define compatible and portable shapes

Advantages

This shape have unique advantages are following:

- The box is portable and compatible in terms of size & weight.
- Dust resistant & corrosion resistant property.
- This shape is used in the market as a product to save fossil gases.

Figure 5: Cuboid shape Structure

III. CONCLUSION

A summary of the production techniques and use of HHO gas has been presented here, highlighting its variability as efficient renewable alternative fuel. The process named electrolysis of water is used for preparation of HHO gas which is an amalgam of hydrogen(H₂) and oxygen(O₂). This type of analysis highlights the uncertainty state regarding laboratory evaluation of the HHO gas ideation. Bubbler tube is an important component for the HHO generator because a negligible amount of moisture is contained inside it. Increasing use of non-renewable sources for domestic purposes is a serious problem for the environment. Renewable sources are the best for a good and healthy environment. As HHO gas has proven to be a great source of power, the use of HHO cells is permissible and very productive.

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